

IOT PRACTICAL TRAINING

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Abstract. For students in engineering colleges, practical training is very important in college so that they can get jobs in companies and develop new products after graduation. It is very important to have practical teaching methods that allow them to think creatively and independently in college. Many educators are conducting education with this in mind. There are many effective methods for practical methods, but I would like to share my method. In my case, the professor gives the students an assignment, and the students have to solve the assignment given by the professor on their own. If necessary, they also ask the AI software. There is equipment required for the lab. First, you will learn how to use this equipment and be trained on how to measure various variables using the equipment. Each class is given a simple project to measure a variable using equipment. They also build hardware that can change the measurement. Students use ChatGPT to find their own answers and discuss them with their peers. Sometimes they write on the whiteboard and explain, while other students share their opinions. The professor only provides directions. Students will develop the ability to design hardware through hands-on practice. They will also learn how to find solutions on their own through the process of carrying out projects and how to collaborate through discussions with their peers. They will also learn how to combine hardware and software by creating software that operates the hardware they have created. The satisfaction level of students who learn this process is very high. As a result, through this hands-on process, students will improve their ability to configure IoT systems.

Keywords: practical training education, measurement, IoT practicing training, Multimeter, Hardware, software

Introduction.

There have been many studies on educational methodology to date [1-5]. However, most of these papers are focused on the field of humanities education. On the other hand, there are some papers on engineering education, but not many [6-7]. Also, papers on practical training education are very rare [8-9].

In the era of the 4th Industrial Revolution, thanks to the development of SNS, we live in a world where everyone in the world can easily access information. Both professors and students can easily access information, and with the development of artificial intelligence, we can receive a lot of help from artificial intelligence software. These days, we can easily find out what professors, students, and engineers in advanced countries such as Korea, the United States, and Europe are thinking and researching through SNS. It is also easy to find out what kind of practical training is needed for this. Professors should always think about how to cultivate future Uzbek talents in this era.

The traditional teaching method is that the professor explains in the classroom, and the students read the textbook, listen to the explanation, and summarize it in their notes. This method is not appropriate for today's times. This method is necessary to some extent for engineering education, especially practical education, but it should not be the main thing. Professors should actively utilize the Internet to allow students to access a lot of information. In particular, they should recommend the use of artificial intelligence apps. It is effective for professors to present

only certain topics, and have students find solutions on the Internet and discuss them with each other.

In addition, universities should encourage practical training. In order for mobile phones and cars produced in Uzbekistan to become the best in the world in the future, it is absolutely necessary for students to have hands-on experience in making basic but small mobile phones and cars themselves. This is because students can learn various basic and applied technologies through the process of making products themselves.

Methodology. How can universities effectively provide engineering education to produce excellent talents? What kind of research should universities conduct, and what kind of education do students want to receive? The role of universities is to develop students' ability to use their creativity to create new results. How can universities educate students to use their creativity? First, it is to stimulate students' interest. The important thing in education is that students, not professors, are the main characters. What should universities do to achieve this?

Professors should always think about these issues and be with their students. Since professors have more experience than students, they can easily grasp the world technology trends and use them to plan practical education for students. It is important for professors to always find new ideas and understand them in detail to maintain students' interest.

Professors are effective in stimulating students' interest by finding and implementing things that students have not thought of and showing them directly to the students. Students with this interest will have a desire to create something on their own. It is important to support these creative students to solve the given tasks on their own and find solutions with their peers. This type of education is called practical education. In order to provide practical education in the IoT field, professors should prepare the following:

- 1) A practice room where students can practice
- 2) Basic equipment for students (multimeter, soldering iron, and other basic equipment)
- 3) Various electronic components for students (semiconductors, resistors, various sensors, etc)
- 4) Computers for students to use

The professor should always observe and study the main character, the student. The professor should figure out what the student wants to study. After figuring out what the student wants to study, he should make a comprehensive practical education plan and figure out the basic theory, practice, and necessary materials or equipment. Then, the professor should suggest a research direction or project to the students and create an environment where the students can solve the problem by themselves. The professor should give the students a basic practical project, and the students should solve the project by themselves.

Results and discussion. There are not many systematic systems or methods for practical training in Uzbekistan universities. In general, in order to systematically conduct IoT practical training, you need to understand the general concept of electricity. Then, you need to start basic practical training using this concept. That is, you need to understand the concept of current, voltage, and resistance and be able to measure each of them using a multimeter. In addition, the development of software to implement such hardware is also important. In this study, we tried various methods to directly provide effective practical training to TUIT students.

Plan for Practical Training. In order to provide effective practical education to students, the professor has developed the following practical education plan. He has planned how to acquire basic theories, prepare the equipment necessary for education, and plan an effective execution process.

Acquire basic theories. We collected and organized basic materials to acquire basic concepts about IoT. All materials were made using Power Point and distributed to students before class.

1.2 A laboratory where students can freely discuss and practice. We have prepared the equipment and materials necessary to practice the basic concepts of IoT. We have prepared digital multimeters, resistors, sensors, switches, semiconductors, breadboards, jumper cables, etc. We have also prepared a small project process for practice. Figures 1, 2, 3, and 4 show the equipment used in this experiment, representing a digital multimeter, sensors and jumper wires, a breadboard, switches and semiconductors, respectively.

Figure 1. Digital Multimeter

Figure 2. Sensors and jumper wires

Figure 3. Bread Boaed

Figure 4. Switches and Semiconductors

And Figure 5 shows the box that stores each part. When students were experimenting, they used the parts they needed from the parts box themselves, and when they finished their practice, they organized the parts in the practice equipment themselves, so that they could feel the neat organization of the parts and the importance of the parts.

Figure 5. Education tool box

Computers used for practice

The most widely used computers in the IoT and IoT fields are Arduino and Raspberry Pi. A picture of Arduino is shown in Figure 6. Arduino is not strictly a computer because it does not have an OS, but is usually called a controller. In order to use Arduino, students learn the C language. Of course, they configure the hardware with practice equipment and write the programs that operate this hardware directly in C. Figure 7 shows the Raspberry Pi computer. Raspberry Pi uses a Linux-based OS and mainly uses the Python language. The Raspberry Pi has 40 I/O pins that can send and receive information to the outside world.

Figure 6. Arduino

Figure 7. Raspberry Pi

1.4 Peripheral equipment

In order to use Arduino and Raspberry Pi computers, peripheral monitors and PCs are required. The university provided all of these equipment, so I was able to practice. The monitor and keyboard set is shown in Figure 8. Figure 9 shows the PC for practicing the Raspberry Pi and the linked system. To use Arduino and Raspberry Pi computers, you need peripheral monitors and PCs. The school provided all of these devices, so I was able to practice. When using Raspberry Pi computers, you need external monitors, keyboards, and mouse sets. The monitor sets used at this time are important elements that make up a single Linux computer system. The monitor and keyboard sets are shown in Figure 8. Figure 9 shows the system connected to the Raspberry Pi practice PC.

Figure 8. Momonitor sets

Figure 9. Computers

The Process of practical training.

2.1 Design Hardware and measurement of basic electrical parameters

Students use the above equipment to directly measure electrical parameters and configure their own hardware to generate the required current. And they practice measuring the variables themselves. If they do not know how to measure, they ask the AI software chatGPT to directly measure the current, voltage, and resistance. They also configure their own hardware to generate the required current. Through this process, students gradually improve their skills. Figure 10 is a photo of students building their own hardware, and Figure 11 is a photo of the hardware the

students created. Once the circuit is constructed, the voltage, current, and resistance are measured directly with a digital multimeter. If the results are not the desired measurements for the students, the circuit is reconstructed and the measurement process is repeated. Figure 12 is a photo of the students directly measuring the values of parts of the circuit with a digital multimeter. Figure 14 is a photo of the resistance circuit redesigned to create the desired current.

Figure 10. Making the hardware

Figure 11. Designed hardware

Figure 12. Measurement

Figure 13. Resistor design

Creating software and discussing

Once the hardware configuration is complete, a program to operate the hardware is written using a computer. All of these processes are done by the students themselves. In the case of Arduino, the C language is used for programming, and in the case of Raspberry Pi, the Python language is mainly used. The operating status of the hardware is checked with the created program, and if a problem occurs, the students discuss it with each other and solve the problem.

Figure 14 Programming

Figure 15 Discussing each other

2.3 Final discussion with Professor

After the students' discussion is over and the circuit and program modifications are completed, they have a final discussion with the professor. They discuss the circuit configuration, measuring the electrical characteristics of each part of the circuit, writing the program, etc., and

discuss whether there are more efficient methods. Finally, the professor makes a final summary and concludes the project. Figure 16 is a photo of the discussion with the professor, and Figure 17 is a photo of the professor's final summary.

Figure 16. Discussion with Professor

Figure 17. Professor's final summary

Conclusion. Using a digital multimeter, students measured the required electrical parameters and constructed a resistance circuit to generate the required current. Through this process, students gained an understanding of basic electrical theory and measurement techniques. In addition, they wrote the operating program of the configured hardware directly in C or Python. Through this process, students improved their programming skills. Students learned how to solve problems on their own when they encountered them by using ChatGPT or Google Chrome to complete the tasks one by one. By solving problems using ChatGPT, a popular AI program these days, students can discover improvements to ChatGPT and acquire basic materials for writing new AI programs on their own.

In order to effectively conduct practical education for students, the qualifications of the instructors are most important. The instructors need to have sufficient knowledge and skills regarding practical education. The instructors need to practice the practical education content sufficiently in advance and identify and prepare for problems that may arise during the practical education process. In addition, essential practical education equipment and materials are needed. The university must prepare these for effective practical education.

Through this practical training, students can naturally learn theory and practical skills, and can utilize their capabilities in society after graduation. In particular, practical training is very important in the engineering field, and university authorities should strengthen practical training. Students who completed this practical training course are very satisfied and thank me. Thanks to this, I am very grateful that I have a positive view of myself and Korea. The purpose of this study is to help Uzbek universities by introducing one of the various practical training programs to Uzbekistan, which is still not active.

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